

FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES UNDER IMPACT LOADING

Young W. Kwon¹

¹ Dept. of Mechanical & Aerospace Eng., Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey CA 93943,
ywkwon@nps.edu

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ABSTRACT

Previous studies showed that the effect of Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) was significant on polymer composite structures under dynamic loading. In this study, fluid coupling effect was examined on composite structures. In other words, fluid was filled between two parallel structures. As one structure is subjected to dynamic loading, the motion of the other structure was examined. The cellular automata techniques were used for this study, and a series of parametric studies were conducted to understand what parameters were important to affect the fluid coupling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been used significantly for aerospace engineering because of their high specific strength and stiffness. Recently, composite materials are also being applied to marine applications such as ships, offshore structures, etc. One of the major components to be considered in marine applications is the fluid like water. Marine applications of composite materials naturally introduce fluid-structure interaction (FSI) of composite structures and fluids which are mostly water. Because polymer composite materials have material densities which are very comparable to that of water, the FSI effect is more important to those composite structures than conventional metallic structures made of steels. As a result, the effect of FSI on polymer composite structures must be fully understood to avoid any premature failure of those structures in applications.

Some of the previous research studied impact loading on composite structures which were in contact with water [1-4]. Those studies suggested that the effect of FSI played a significant role in the failure loads and failure locations. Because FSI activated higher modes of vibration, the vibrational shape with FSI is so much different from that without FSI for the same composite structures. Furthermore, such a different vibrational mode shape can result in a change in the location for the largest strain/stress.

In this study, coupling of structures through a fluid medium is studied numerically. To this end, a new numerical scheme was developed and presented. The next section describes the numerical techniques for the fluid and structural domains, which is followed by a series of numerical examples. Then, conclusions are provided.

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

Analysis of FSI requires solvers for both structural and fluid problems. Recently, the Cellular Automata (CA) technique has been developed for structural analysis and the wave equation. If a fluid is fully confined inside a structure and its viscosity is neglected, the fluid medium may be represented using the wave equation. As a result, the wave equation was used for the present study. CA techniques for beam and plate structures as well as the wave equation are presented below.

The CA technique uses a set of rules at each cell, and the same rules are applied to all cells repeatedly as time progresses or until the solution converges [5,6]. As a result, this technique is very easy to program for parallel computing and computationally efficient. Very recently, the Finite Differenced based Cellular Automata (FDCA) was developed [7] and it is presented here.

The differential equations for beam bending is written as below

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= EI \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\
 m \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} &= -\frac{\partial^2 M}{\partial x^2} + p
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where M and w are the bending moment and the transverse displacement of the beam, respectively, and EI represents the beam rigidity. In addition, m and p are the linear density of the mass and the load intensity per unit length. Then, x and t are the spatial and temporal coordinate variables. Applying the finite difference technique to the above differential equations yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_i^t &= (EI)_i (w_{i+1}^t + w_{i-1}^t - 2w_i^t) / (\Delta x)^2 \\
 \ddot{w}_i^t &= \left[(-M_{i+1}^t - M_{i-1}^t + 2M_i^t) / (\Delta x)^2 + p_i^t \right] / m_i \\
 \dot{w}_i^{t+\Delta t} &= \dot{w}_i^t + \ddot{w}_i^t (\Delta t) \\
 w_i^{t+\Delta t} &= w_i^t + \dot{w}_i^{t+\Delta t} (\Delta t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Here, Δt and Δx are the time and spatial sizes, and the superimposed dot indicates the temporal derivative. The subscript indicates the cell number. The boundary conditions are applied as below.

For a simply supported boundary, the boundary cell has zero displacement and zero bending moment. A clamped boundary needs a fictitious cell. Then, the clamped cell has zero displacement, and the fictitious cell is assigned to have the same displacement as that of the next cell to the clamped cell. This is to apply the zero slope condition. A free boundary cell is similar to a clamped boundary cell requiring a fictitious cell while bending moment M replaces the transverse displacement w .

Plate bending has the following governing equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= D \nabla^2 w \\
 m \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} &= -\nabla^2 M + q
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

in which $M = (M_x + M_y) / (1 + \nu)$, and M_x and M_y are the bending moment per unit length about the x and y axes, respectively. The plate rigidity is $D = \frac{Eh^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}$ where E and ν are elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively, and h is the plate thickness. Finally, m and q are the areal mass density and pressure loading.

The FDCA rules for the plate bending problem are presented below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{i,j}^t &= D_{i,j} \left[(w_{i+1,j}^t + w_{i-1,j}^t - 2w_{i,j}^t) / (\Delta x)^2 + (w_{i,j+1}^t + w_{i,j-1}^t - 2w_{i,j}^t) / (\Delta y)^2 \right] \\
 \ddot{w}_{i,j}^t &= \left[(-M_{i+1,j}^t - M_{i-1,j}^t + 2M_{i,j}^t) / (\Delta x)^2 + (-M_{i,j+1}^t - M_{i,j-1}^t + 2M_{i,j}^t) / (\Delta y)^2 + q_{i,j}^t \right] / m_{i,j} \\
 \dot{w}_{i,j}^{t+\Delta t} &= \dot{w}_{i,j}^t + \ddot{w}_{i,j}^t (\Delta t) \\
 w_{i,j}^{t+\Delta t} &= w_{i,j}^t + \dot{w}_{i,j}^{t+\Delta t} (\Delta t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where subscripts indicate the cell location in the 2-D plane. Applying boundary conditions to the plate bending problem is similar to that for the beam bending problem as discussed above.

For the fluid medium, the acoustic wave equation is used as given below:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 \phi \tag{5}$$

Here ϕ and c denote the velocity potential and the wave speed of the fluid medium. The fluid velocity is expressed in terms of the velocity potential as below:

$$\vec{v} = \nabla \phi \quad (6)$$

and pressure is computed from the velocity potential like

$$p = -\rho_o \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \quad (7)$$

The FDCA procedure for the wave equation results in

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\phi}_{i,j}^t &= c_{i,j}^2 \left[(\phi_{i+1,j}^t + \phi_{i-1,j}^t - 2\phi_{i,j}^t) / (\Delta x)^2 + (\phi_{i,j+1}^t + \phi_{i,j-1}^t - 2\phi_{i,j}^t) / (\Delta y)^2 \right] \\ \dot{\phi}_{i,j}^{t+\Delta t} &= \dot{\phi}_{i,j}^t + \ddot{\phi}_{i,j}^t (\Delta t) \\ \phi_{i,j}^{t+\Delta t} &= \phi_{i,j}^t + \dot{\phi}_{i,j}^{t+\Delta t} (\Delta t) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

3 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

As an example, a 2-D fluid medium is confined by two flexible beams as sketched in Figure 1. Both beams are simply supported at each end. An excitation was given to the bottom side beam, and the responses of both beams as well as the pressure propagation in the fluid medium were examined. To this end, a parametric study was conducted. The base case used the following properties; $L_x=L_y=1$ m, beam rigidity 166.7 Nm^2 , lineal mass density of beam 2 Kg/m , fluid speed of sound 1500 m/s , and fluid density 1000 kg/m^3 . The excitation to the bottom beam was a uniform pressure with a harmonic function like $p(t) = p_o \sin(\omega t)$ where $p_o = 1000 \text{ N/m}$ and $\omega = 5,000/\pi \text{ Hz}$. Figure 2 plots the beam displacements of top and bottom beams at their centers while Figure 3 shows fluid velocity potential contours for the base case. Because the fluid contours vary with time, all the contour plots were selected at the end of the computational time, which is also representative of fluid pressure throughout the motion. The displacement of the top beam is much smaller than that of the bottom beam suggesting a weak coupling.

Figure 1: Fluid bounded by flexible beams.

As L_y is reduced to 0.5 m , there is a strong coupling between the two beams. The displacement of the top beam becomes much greater than the base case as seen in Figure 4. The fluid velocity potential contour in Figure 5 looks like the half of that in Figure 3. As L_y is further reduced to 0.25 m , 0.1 m and 0.05 m , respectively, coupling of both beams becomes stronger as shown in Figures 6 through 8. Figure 9 compares the maximum central displacements of both top and bottom beams as a function of the gap size between them, which is filled with fluid. The figure suggests that the smaller the gap is, the greater the coupling between the two structures is. This was somehow expected. A further study showed that the fluid coupling is negligible if the fluid gap size is at least the length of the beam.

When the fluid gap is small, the vibrational period of both beams are clearly influenced by the fluid gap. As the gap size becomes smaller, the period becomes smaller and both beams respond with the same period. When the gap size is less than or equal to 0.1 m , the reduction in the vibrational period is quite linear to the gap size.

Figure 2: Beam displacements of the base case.

Figure 3: Fluid velocity potential contours in fluid domain for the base case.

The next case simply changed the excitation frequency to $50/\pi\text{ Hz}$ while the rest of the parameters remained the same as before except of L_y which was fixed as 0.25 m . Figures 11 and 12 plot the central displacement of both beams as well as the fluid velocity potential contour. The beam response with 100 Hz is very different from previous cases. The beam moves with superposition of two clear frequencies. However, when the excitation frequency was further reduced to $25/\pi\text{ Hz}$, the high frequency component starts to disappear again.

The speed of sound in the fluid medium does not affect the fluid coupling effect unless the fluid density is varied. While the speed of sound remained constant, a change in fluid density influenced the fluid coupling. Reduction in fluid density decreased the vibrational period, i.e., increased the vibrational frequency and magnitude.

Figure 4: Beam displacements for $L_y=0.5$ m.

Figure 5: Fluid velocity potential contours in fluid domain for $L_y=0.5$ m.

Figure 6: Beam displacements for $L_y=0.25$ m.

Figure 7: Beam displacements for $L_y=0.1$ m.

Figure 8: Beam displacements for $L_y=0.05$ m.

Figure 9: Plot of maximum displacement at the center of each beam for different sizes of gap (L_y).

Figure 10: Plot of vibrational periods of beam responses for different sizes of gap (L_y).

Figure 11: Beam displacements for $50/\pi$ Hz.

Figure 12: Fluid velocity potential contours in fluid domain for 100 Hz.

Figure 13: Pressure contours in fluid domain for $25/\pi$ Hz.

All previous cases considered identical two beams in their material and geometric properties. This time, the stiffness of the top beam was varied. For this study, the spacing was fixed as $L_y=0.1$ m. Figure 14 shows the beam responses as the top beam has one quarter of the beam rigidity of the bottom beam. As seen in the figure, the vibrational magnitude increases but the vibrational frequency decreases. Figure 15 plots the change in vibrational frequency as a function of the beam rigidity ratio which was computed as the top beam rigidity divided by bottom beam rigidity. The results indicate the vibrational period decreases as the top beam rigidity increases. The next study changed the density of the top beam while its beam rigidity was the same as that of the bottom beam. In this case, the vibrational frequency did not change.

Figure 14: Beam displacements with top beam rigidity as one quarter of the bottom beam rigidity.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Fluid coupling on composite structures was investigated numerically. Both structures and fluid were modelled using the CA technique which is computational efficient and easy to program. In order to understand the fluid coupling, a series of parametric studies were conducted. The results showed that if the spacing between the two structures is greater than the structural length, fluid coupling is negligible. As the spacing becomes smaller, the coupling becomes larger. The spacing influenced both the maximum displacements of the structures as well as the vibrational frequencies of the structures. The excitation frequency also affected the coupling effect.

Figure 15: Plot of vibrational period as function of ratio of the beam rigidity.

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